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Forage and seed yield of velvet bean (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.)) as affected by sowing date and plant spacing under irrigated condition, Gezira state, Sudan

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ABSTRACT

Velvet bean (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.)) can be used as food, feed (forage and seeds) and environmental services. Also, the plant can be a cover crop and green manure. Experiments was carried out during the seasons of 2017/18 and 2018/19 at the Experimental Farm of the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, University of Gezira. Experiment aimed to evaluate the effect of three sowing date (15th of September, 15th of December and 15th of March) and three plant spacing (15, 30 and 45 cm) on forage and seed yield of velvet bean. The treatments were arranged in split –plot design, where sowing date assigned as main plot and plant spacing as sub-plot with four replications. Results showed that the effect of sowing date, plant spacing and their interaction on fresh forage yield, number of pods per plant, number of seeds per pod and seed yield was highly significantly different. Plant spacing 30 cm and 15th of September sowing date produced the highest fresh forage and seed yield (21.97 and 3.85 ton ha⁻¹), respectively. Based on the experimental results obtained from this study it could be recommended that the best combination for forage production and seed yield during different seasons is 15th of September sowing date and 30 cm plant spacing.

Keywords: Velvet bean, sowing date, plant spacing and yield, *Mucuna pruriens*

1. INTRODUCTION

Velvet bean (*Mucuna pruriens* (L.) DC. var. *utilis* (Wall. ex Wight) Baker ex Burck) belongs to the legume family Fabaceae, which is the third largest among flowering plants consisting of approximately 650 genera and 20,000 species [1]. Fabaceae is the second most important plant source of human and animal nutrition [2]. Velvet bean originated from southern Asia and Malaysia and is now widely distributed in the tropics [3]. It requires a hot moist climate with annual rainfall ranging from 650 to 2500 mm and a long frost-free growing season during the wet months. It can grow on a wide range of soils, from sands to clays, but thrives on well-drained, light textured soils of appreciable acidity [3 and 4]. It is annual or sometimes short-lived perennial. Velvet bean can be used as food, feed (forage and seeds) and environmental services. Also, the plant can be a cover crop and green manure. It is a valuable fodder and feed legume. Vines and foliage can be used as pasture, hay or silage for ruminants, while pods and seeds can be ground into a meal and fed to both ruminants and monogastrics [5 and 6].

The crop gives reliable yields in dry farming and low soil fertility conditions that do not allow the profitable cultivation of most other food legumes [7]. Yields of green fodder may be up to 10-35 t/ha resulting in 8.2-16.4 t DM/ha and yields of hay average 2.8-3.6 t/ha [8]. Depending on stage of maturity, CP in foliage DM 11–23%, and 20–35% in the grain. High mineral, i.e. K, Mg, Ca and Fe, and lysine contents in grain. Digestibility of foliage 60–65%, grain >95% and husks 78%. Tried mainly for protein supplementation in bovines, sheep and goats. As an example, a daily live weight gain of 60 g/animal compared to 44 g with commercial concentrates has been obtained with sheep. Also, velvet bean hay has been successfully substituted for dairy concentrates in Zimbabwe without decline in milk yield or quality and has been recommended for this purpose [9].

In Sudan, there is always scarcity in forage at the end of winter and during the summer seasons. At the same time there is a high need for feed during this time of the year. Hence there is a need to bridge this feed gap. Velvet bean eventually stands as a promising option, but information about it is limited. The main objective of these study is to recommend the cultural practices including sowing date, spacing to obtain high forage yield and seed yield of velvet bean.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Experimental site

The experiments was conducted at the experimental farm of the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences, University of Gezira, which is located at an altitude of 405 m+MSL (mean sea level), latitude 14.4° N and longitude 33 5° E in Wad Medani in Central Sudan, during the summer seasons of 2017/18 and 2018/19. The soils are predominantly typical vertisols that expand and shrink markedly with changes in moisture content and develop deep vertical drying cracks. These soils developed from deposits carried by the Blue Nile from the Ethiopian Highlands. Clay content may reach 60% or more throughout the soil profile. The content of organic carbon and nitrogen is very low [10 and 11].

The range of climate of the central clay plains of Sudan as classified by [12] extends from tropical continental desert in the North to tropical sub-humid in the South. Recently it was

found that Gezira State has three climatic zones, semi-desert in the North, dry in the center and semi-dry in the South (Adam, 2014). The Gezira Scheme area lies within the dry zone, which is characterized by low average annual rainfall of about 150 to 350 mm and clear fluctuation in the distribution and intensity of rainfall from year to year. Maximum temperature ranges from 34 °C in January to 42 °C in May, while the minimum temperature ranges between 14 and 25 °C in January and June, respectively. The relative humidity is low most of the year, 50% is the mean relative humidity for the months between October and June.

2. 2. Experiment

The experiment was carried out during the seasons of 2017/18 and 2018/19 to evaluate the effect of three sowing date namely 15th September, 15th December and 15th March and three plant spacing of 15, 30 and 45 cm on forage and seed yield of velvet bean. The treatments were arranged in split –plot design, where sowing date assigned as main plot and plant spacing as sub-plot with four replications.

2. 3. Cultural practices

Land preparation involved disc ploughing, harrowing, leveling and then ridging to 80 cm apart ridges. The plot size was 5m × 4m. Two seeds were sown per hole in all spacings. Velvet bean was harvested at 80% flowering for forage yield determination.

The harvested area was two meter long from the middle of the ridge in plot (3.2 m²).

2. 4. Growth, yield and yield components measured

- a) **Total fresh forage yield (ton/ha):** Fresh forage yield was immediately weighed in the field in kg/m² and then converted to ton/ha.
- b) **Number of pods/plant:** As average number of pods of ten plants which were randomly selected in each plot
- c) **Number of seeds/pod:** As average number of seeds of ten pods which were randomly selected in each plot..
- d) **100 seed weight/g:** Three samples each containing hundred seed was randomly counted from the final seed yield for each plot and then the seeds were weighted using a sensitive balance and the mean seed weight was determined .
- e) **Seeds yield (ton/ha):** The harvested area (2 m²) was 1.25 meter long from ridge in plot. Seed samples were threshed manually and the seeds were weighed to determine the final seed yield.

2. 5. Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was done using GenStat software and Least significant differences (LSD) was used to show the significance differences between mean.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1. Fresh forage yield (ton ha⁻¹)

The fresh forage yield of velvet bean was significantly affected by sowing date in both seasons (Tables 1 and 2). The fresh forage yield was decreased by delaying sowing date in both

seasons. The highest fresh forage yield was obtained by the 15th of september sowing date (24.55 and 16.04 ton ha⁻¹) and the lowest fresh forage yield was obtained by the 15 March sowing date (11.86 and 6.79 ton ha⁻¹) in the both seasons. This may be due to relatively cool temperature and insufficient time available for the growth and development to these seeds before low temperatures creep in, which could have promoted the growth of the plants. At higher temperature the germination is rapid but plant stand is affected and because of this the yield in earliest sowing date is high.

Significant differences were detected among the plant spacing on fresh forage yield of velvet bean in both seasons (Tables 1 and 2). The highest fresh forage yield was obtained by the plant spacing of 30 cm (18.42 and 12.33 ton ha⁻¹) and the lowest fresh forage yield was obtained by the plant spacing of 45 cm (14.62 and 10.21 ton ha⁻¹) in the both seasons. The probable reason for maximum fresh forage yield in the plant spacing of 30 cm could be competition of plants for light that results in fresh forage yield. These results were in line with the findings of [13] who found that, plant spacing of 30 cm resulted in better stand count, taller plant, higher number of branches and forage yield per plant for velvet bean.

The interaction effect of sowing date and plant spacing on fresh forage yield of velvet bean was not significant in both seasons (Tables 1 and 2). Even though, the highest fresh forage yield was achieved by the 15th of September sowing date and plant spacing of 30 cm (27.27 and 16.67 ton ha⁻¹ in the first and second seasons, respectively). These results support the findings of [8] who reported that, velvet bean yield range from 10 to 35 ton ha⁻¹. [14] stated that a crop of velvet bean yielded 17.4 ton ha⁻¹ in north Queensland. Also, [15] obtained a yield of 11. 176 ton ha⁻¹ of green matter from velvet bean in coastal Queensland, Australia. The probable reason for it could be that early- planted crop had sufficient time for its growth and development.

Table 1. Effect of sowing date, plant spacing and their interaction on fresh forage yield (ton ha⁻¹) of velvet bean during the summer season of 2017/2018

Plant spacing	Sowing date			Mean
	15 Sept.	15 Dec.	15 Mar.	
15 cm	26.06	17.50	11.46	18.34
30 cm	27.27	15.02	12.97	18.42
45 cm	20.32	12.40	11.15	14.62
Mean	24.55	14.97	11.86	
SE± Sowing date	2.113*			
SE± Plant spacing	0.839**			
SE± Interaction	2.426ns			
C.V. (%)	14.5			

Table 2. Effect of sowing date, plant spacing and their interaction on fresh forage yield (ton ha⁻¹) of velvet bean during the season 2018/2019.

Plant spacing	Sowing date			Mean
	15 Sept.	15 Dec.	15 Mar.	
15 cm	16.25	12.40	6.89	11.84
30 cm	16.67	11.25	9.07	12.33
45 cm	15.21	10.99	4.43	10.21
Mean	16.04	11.55	6.79	
SE± Sowing date	0.517**			
SE± Plant spacing	0.509*			
SE± Interaction	0.885 ^{ns}			
C.V. (%)	13.3			

3. 2. Number of pods/plant

In both seasons, the effect of sowing date on number of pods per plant was highly significantly different ($P \leq 0.001$) (Tables 3 and 4). The number of pods per plant was decreased by delaying sowing date and the 15th March sowing date failed to produce seed from velvet bean in both seasons.

The highest number of pods per plant was obtained by the 15 September sowing date (16 and 17) in the both seasons. It may be due to air temperature. Also, [16] indicated that the air temperature affects the pod number per plant. While the pod number was the lowest at the temperature of 20 °C / 16 °C (day / night), it increased to a maximum at the temperature of 28 °C / 24 °C, and then it started to decrease when the temperature reached 32 °C / 28 °C.

Table 3. Effect of sowing date, plant spacing and their interaction on number of pods/plant of velvet bean during the summer season of 2017/2018

Plant spacing	Sowing date			Mean
	15 Sept.	15 Dec.	15 Mar.	
15 cm	15.97	10.56	0	8.84
30 cm	18.33	16.75	0	11.69
45 cm	13.11	17.11	0	10.07

Mean	15.81	14.20	0	
SE± Sowing date	0.381***			
SE± Plant spacing	0.715*			
SE± Interaction	1.08*			
C.V. (%)	21			

These results are in conformity with the findings of [16] who reported that the differences between sowing dates for the pod number per plant were statistically significant. The effect of plant spacing on number of pods per plant was significant (Tables 3 and 4). The highest number of pods per plant was obtained by the 30 cm plant spacing (12 and 11) in the both seasons. The interaction effect of sowing date and plant spacing on number of pods per plant was significant in both seasons (Tables 3 and 4). The highest number of pods per plant was obtained by the 15 September sowing date and 30 cm plant spacing (18) in the first season, while the highest number of pods per plant was obtained by the 15 September sowing date and 15 cm plant spacing (19) in the second season.

Table 4. Effect of sowing date, plant spacing and their interaction on number of pods/plant of velvet bean during the summer season of 2018/2019

Plant spacing	Sowing date			Mean
	15 Sept.	15 Dec.	15 Mar.	
15 cm	19.19	12.13	0	10.44
30 cm	17.64	15.57	0	11.07
45 cm	12.97	17.50	0	10.16
Mean	16.60	15.06	0	
SE± Sowing date	0.155***			
SE± Plant spacing	0.136***			
SE± Interaction	0.247***			
C.V. (%)	3.9			

3. 3. Number of seeds/pod

Highly significant differences ($P \leq 0.001$) were found among sowing dates in number of seeds per pod of velvet bean (Tables 5 and 6). The number of seeds per pod decreased by

delaying sowing date. The highest number of seeds per pod was obtained by the 15th September sowing date (5.3 and 5.16), followed by 15th December (4.39 and 4.5) in both seasons. This may be due to climatic conditions, particularly temperature degree, photoperiodicity, and relative humidity.

The effect of plant spacing on number of seeds per pod was significant (Tables 5 and 6). The largest number of seeds per pod obtained by the 30 cm plant spacing (3.3 and 3.39) in the both seasons. The probable reason for maximum number of seeds per pod in the plant spacing of 30 cm could be competition of plants for light that results in number of seeds per pod and mean that the 30 cm spacing gave the optimum plant density for seed production in velvet bean.

Table 5. Effect of sowing date, plant spacing and their interaction on number of seeds per pod of velvet bean during the summer season of 2017/2018

Plant spacing	Sowing date			Mean
	15 Sept.	15 Dec.	15 Mar.	
15 cm	4.77	4.35	0	3.04
30 cm	5.03	4.88	0	3.30
45 cm	5.30	3.93	0	3.08
Mean	50.3	4.39	0	
SE± Sowing date	0.128***			
SE± Plant spacing	0.045***			
SE± Interaction	0.143***			
C.V. (%)	4.3			

Table 6. Effect of sowing date, plant spacing and their interaction on number of seeds per pod of velvet bean during the summer season of 2018/2019

Plant spacing	Sowing date			Mean
	15 Sept.	15 Dec.	15 Mar.	
15 cm	5.05	4.73	0	3.26
30 cm	5.33	4.84	0	3.39
45 cm	5.12	3.92	0	3.01
Mean	5.16	4.50	0	

SE± Sowing date	0.012***
SE± Plant spacing	0.012***
SE± Interaction	0.021***
C.V. (%)	1.2

The interaction effect of sowing date and plant spacing on number of seeds per pod was highly significant ($P \leq 0.001$) in both seasons (Tables 5 and 6). The highest number of seeds per pod was obtained by the 15 September sowing date and 45 cm plant spacing (5) in the first season, but no significant differences were found between the 15 September sowing date and 15 and 30 cm plant spacing. Whereas, the highest number of seeds per pod was obtained by the 15 September sowing date and 30 cm plant spacing (5) in the second season. Results were in line with [17] who reported that velvet bean produced about 4 to 8 seeds per pod.

3. 4. 100 seed weight (g)

Sowing date had a highly significant effect on 100 seed weight in both seasons (Tables 7 and 8). The 15 March sowing date of velvet bean failed to produce seeds in both seasons. The highest 100 seed weight was obtained by the 15 September sowing date (114 and 107 g in the first and second seasons, respectively). These is due to high temperature at the later stage of the crop which reduced the seed size as evident by weight of 100 seeds. The results are in similarity with that of [18] who reported that sowing dates were significantly affected by 100-seeds weight.

Table 7. Effect of sowing date, plant spacing and their interaction on 100 seed weight (g) of velvet bean during the summer season of 2017/2018

Plant spacing	Sowing date			Mean
	15 Sept.	15 Dec.	15 Mar.	
15 cm	108.13	106.57	0	71.57
30 cm	117.00	103.40	0	73.47
45 cm	116.90	119.98	0	78.96
Mean	114.01	109.98	0	
SE± Sowing date	1.561***			
SE± Plant spacing	1.596*			
SE± Interaction	2.744*			
C.V. (%)	6.4			

Results showed that there were significant differences ($P \leq 0.05$) among the plant spacing on 100 seed weight. The 100 seed weight was increased by increasing plant spacing. The highest 100 seed weight was obtained by the 45 cm plant spacing (79 and 73 g in the both seasons).

The interaction effect of sowing date and plant spacing on 100 seed weight was significant ($P \leq 0.05$) (Tables 7 and 8). The highest 100 seed weight was obtained by the 15 December sowing date and 45 cm plant spacing (119.98 g) in the first season. On the other hand, the heaviest 100 seed weight was obtained by the 15 December sowing date and 45 cm plant spacing (110.06 g) and 15 September sowing date and 30 cm plant spacing (110.36 g) in the second season, but no significant differences were found between the 15 September sowing date and 30 and 45 cm plant spacing and the 15 December sowing date and 45 cm plant spacing.

The results are in similarity with that of [18] who reported that sowing dates were significantly affected by 100-seeds weight. Similar results were also obtained by [7] who found that 100 seed weight varied from 25 to 110 g. These results in agreement with [19] who evaluate the influence of three different spacings and three fertilizer levels on growth, fodder yield and seed yield attributes of velvet bean. The results revealed that, except yield, all the parameters including growth components were non-significantly ($P > 0.05$) influenced from interactions of various levels of spacings and fertilizer levels.

Table 8. Effect of sowing date, plant spacing and their interaction on 100 seed weight (g) of velvet bean during the summer season of 2018/2019

Plant spacing	Sowing date			Mean
	15 Sept.	15 Dec.	15 Mar.	
15 cm	100.75	96.16	0	65.64
30 cm	110.36	96.57	0	68.98
45 cm	109.18	110.06	0	73.08
Mean	106.64	100.93	0	
SE± Sowing date	0.037***			
SE± Plant spacing	1.469*			
SE± Interaction	2.279*			
C.V. (%)	2.2			

3. 5. Seed yield (ton ha⁻¹)

The seed yield of velvet bean was significantly affected by the sowing date in both seasons (Table 9 and 10). The 15th of March sowing date failed to produce seed from velvet bean. The highest seed yield was obtained by the 15th of September sowing date (2.35 and 2.45

ton ha⁻¹) in the both seasons. On the other hand, the effect of plant spacing on seed yield was highly significant. The highest seed yield was achieved by the 30 cm plant spacing (1.85 and 2.11 ton ha⁻¹), in both seasons (Tables 9 and 10). This is because there was high competition for sunlight, hence growing taller. It was probably due to availability of optimum temperature to the crop for the growth and development stage by sowing during this period. With delay in sowing, as the temperatures slide down, the growth gets slowed down and the number of days to flowering increase. These results are in agreement with [13] who reported that Plant spacing interval of 30 cm resulted in better stand count, taller plant, higher number of branches and forage yield per plant. The increased seed yield was mainly due to increased pod yield, number of pods per plant and number of pods per bunch.

The interaction effect of sowing date and plant spacing on seed yield was highly significant. The highest seed yield was acquired by the 30 cm plant spacing and 15 September sowing date (3.88 and 4.15 ton ha⁻¹) in both seasons.

Table 9. Effect of sowing date, plant spacing and their interaction on seed yield (ton ha⁻¹) of velvet bean during the summer season of 2017/2018

Plant spacing	Sowing date			Mean
	15 Sept.	15 Dec.	15 Mar.	
15 cm	2.20	1.57	0	1.26
30 cm	3.88	1.68	0	1.85
45 cm	0.97	1.35	0	0.77
Mean	2.35	1.53	0	
SE± Sowing date	0.175***			
SE± Plantspacing	0.107***			
SE± Interaction	0.231***			
C.V. (%)	24.7			

These results were in line with [8] who reported that seed yield ranged from 0.25 to 3.3 ton seeds/ha depending on the cultivation conditions. Also, agreed with [20] who found that seed yield ranged from 0.70 to 1.10 ton ha⁻¹ in India, 1.7 to 2.2 ton ha⁻¹ in USA. Yield up to 5 ton ha⁻¹ have been recorded from well managed irrigated crop provided with stakes [21 and 22]. [23] reported that the integrated nutrient combination involving organic form of manures (cocopeat at 5 t/ha and farmyard manure at 12.5 t/ha) and inorganic fertilizers (NPK 40:30:30 kg/ha) resulted in high seed yield. I. Also, [24] reported that in Zimbabwe the average seed yields range from 1.5–2 and 0.5–1 tonnes in natural regions II and IV, respectively. Mucuna can yield up to 2 tonnes of clean seed per hectare. These results in agreement with [19] who reported that except yield, all the parameters including growth components were non-

significantly ($P>0.05$) influenced from interactions of various levels of spacings and fertilizer levels. In contrast [25] reported that there was no significant effect of plant density on seed yield, days to first flower, or on percentage cover at flowering when velvetbean cultivars were planted at three within-row distances (0.15 m, 0.3 m, 0.45 m) and a spacing of 0.6 m between rows.

Table 10. Effect of sowing date, plant spacing and their interaction on seed yield (ton ha⁻¹) of velvet bean during the summer season of 2018/2019

Plant spacing	Sowing date			Mean
	15 Sept.	15 Dec.	15 Mar.	
15 cm	2.06	1.56	0	1.21
30 cm	4.15	2.18	0	2.11
45 cm	1.13	1.24	0	0.79
Mean	2.45	1.66	0	
SE± Sowing date	0.013***			
SE± Plant spacing	0.007***			
SE± Interaction	0.016***			
C.V. (%)	1.6			

4. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Effect of sowing date and plant spacing on forage and seed yield of velvet bean showed that:

- The fresh forage yield of velvet bean was significantly affected by sowing date and plant spacing.
- The highest fresh forage yield was obtained by the 15th of september sowing date and by the plant spacing of 30 cm.
- Sowing date, plant spacing, combined and their interaction have a significant effect on the number of pods per plant, number of seeds per pod, 100 seed weight and seed yield.

Based on the experimental results obtained from this study it could be recommended that the best combination for forage production and seed yield during different seasons is 15 September sowing date and plant spacing of 30 cm.

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